

RESEARCH ARTICLE

ETHNIC AND CLINICAL DISPARITIES IN COLORECTAL CANCER OUTCOMES IN SABAH, MALAYSIA: A POPULATION-BASED STUDY (2015-2020)**Bondi, M.E.^{1*}, Syed Abdul Rahim, S.S.², Ahmad Hijaz, M.H.A.², Mohd Hayati, M.F.², Avoi, R.²**¹ Training Institute Ministry of Health Malaysia Kota Kinabalu, Jalan Kolej Kejururawatan, Off Jalan Kolam Minintod, 88300 Kota Kinabalu, Sabah, Malaysia.² Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Jalan UMS, 88400 Kota Kinabalu, Sabah, Malaysia.

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Abstract

Background: Colorectal cancer (CRC) is a major cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide. In Malaysia, CRC is the most commonly diagnosed cancer among men and the second most common among women. Sabah, characterised by ethnic diversity and healthcare access disparities, lacks population-level data on CRC outcomes. This study aimed to evaluate ethnic and clinical disparities in CRC incidence, survival, and relapse in Sabah and to assess the impact of tumour stage and treatment delay on prognosis.

Methodology: A retrospective cohort analysis of 450 histologically confirmed CRC patients from the Sabah Cancer Registry (2015-2020) was conducted. Kaplan-Meier methods were used to estimate overall and relapse-free survival, while multivariate regression models identified predictors of mortality and relapse.

Results: The median age at diagnosis was 62 years old, with males comprising 55.3% of patients. Chinese patients accounted for 34.3% of cases, followed by Kadazan-Dusun (25.3%), and Bajau (18.8%). Most patients (59.9%) presented with advanced-stage disease. The five-year overall survival rate was 23.2%, and the median relapse-free survival was 24 months. Treatment delay beyond 60 days and diagnosis at an advanced stage were significant predictors of both relapse and mortality. Ethnic disparities were observed in unadjusted outcomes but were no longer significant after adjustment for clinical and geographic variables.

Conclusion: The findings underscore the need for regionally tailored screening programmes, timely treatment pathways, and equitable oncology services to improve CRC outcomes in Sabah. Strengthening early detection and post-treatment surveillance is critical to addressing structural barriers and reducing disparities across Sabah's diverse population.

Keywords: colorectal cancer, survival, ethnic disparities, treatment delay, Sabah, relapse

Introduction

CRC is among the top three most commonly diagnosed cancers globally and is the second leading cause of cancer-related mortality. In 2020 alone, CRC accounted for approximately 1.9 million new cases and over 930,000 deaths, representing 10% of the global cancer burden (Ferlay et al., 2021). The increasing incidence is attributed to ageing populations, dietary transitions, sedentary lifestyles, and disparities in access to early detection and treatment services.

In Malaysia, CRC is the most common cancer among men and the second most common among women, contributing to 13.5% of all cancers diagnosed between 2012 and 2016 (Azizah et al., 2019). The age-standardised incidence rates (ASR) are higher among men (14.8 per 100,000) compared to women (11.1 per 100,000) (MOH, 2017). Ethnic disparities have been documented nationally, with the Chinese population exhibiting the highest incidence, followed by Malays and Indians. Recent studies have highlighted persistent barriers to CRC screening in Malaysia, including limited awareness, cultural beliefs, and accessibility issues, particularly among rural and indigenous populations (Doraimuthu et al., 2023; Ghazali et al., 2021; Ramanathan et al., 2022).

Sabah, Malaysia's second-largest state, is home to a diverse multiethnic population including Chinese, Kadazan-Dusun, Bajau, Murut, Rungus, and Suluk. These populations differ not only in genetic predisposition and dietary habits but also in healthcare accessibility (Kaur et al., 2020). Urban Chinese communities are typically located near tertiary healthcare centres, while indigenous groups often reside in rural or remote areas with limited transportation, diagnostic capacity, and specialist care. In this study, rurality refers to geographic remoteness and limited access to oncology services, consistent with World Health Organization (WHO) definitions.

There is growing attention to the rise of early-onset CRC, typically defined as a diagnosis before the age of 50. Globally, this subgroup has shown increasing incidence, particularly in Asia and among populations undergoing rapid lifestyle transitions (Siegel et al., 2020). Younger individuals are frequently excluded from standard screening guidelines and may present with more aggressive disease, contributing to diagnostic delays. While early-onset CRC was not the primary focus of this study, a stratified analysis was conducted to explore its occurrence.

This study investigated CRC trends in Sabah from 2015 to 2020, focusing on the associations between socio-demographic factors (age, gender, ethnicity, residence) and clinical characteristics (disease stage, treatment type, treatment delay) with key outcomes such as survival and relapse. The findings aim to support culturally appropriate and region-specific strategies to improve CRC outcomes in Sabah's diverse population.

To address these knowledge gaps, this study provides the first population-based analysis of ethnical and clinical disparities in CRC outcomes in Sabah. It evaluates incidence, survival, and relapse across ethnic groups and geographic locations while identifying clinical predictors such as stage at diagnosis and treatment delays. The findings aim to inform targeted, region-specific interventions and guide equitable colorectal cancer control strategies in East Malaysia.

Methods

Study design

This was a retrospective cohort study using data from the Sabah Cancer Registry, encompassing patients diagnosed with CRC between January 2015 and December 2020. The data included comprehensive demographic, clinical, and treatment information.

Participants

Eligible participants were patients with histologically confirmed CRC residing in Sabah. Inclusion criteria were complete demographic and clinical data. Patients diagnosed prior to 2015, those with recurrent CRC, or incomplete clinical records were excluded. A total of 450 patients met the inclusion criteria for this study.

Variables

Demographic variables included age at diagnosis, gender (male/female), ethnicity (Chinese, Kadazan-Dusun, Bajau, Murut, Rungus, Suluk, and others), and residential location (urban/rural). Rurality was defined as geographic remoteness with limited access to tertiary oncology services (WHO, 2021). Clinical variables included tumour histology (adenocarcinoma versus others), location (right colon, left colon, rectum), tumour differentiation (well, moderate, poor), and cancer stage according to the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC 8th Edition). Treatment-related variables included primary treatment modality (curative surgery or chemotherapy) and treatment delay, defined as initiation of definitive treatment occurring more than 60 days after histological diagnosis.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics were summarised using frequencies and percentages for categorical data and medians with interquartile ranges (IQR) for continuous variables. Kaplan-Meier analysis was employed to estimate overall and relapse-free survival, with group comparisons using the log-rank test. Multivariate logistic regression was used to identify independent predictors of mortality and relapse. Variables included in the models were age, gender, ethnicity, disease stage, and treatment delay. Statistical analyses were performed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software, version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA), and a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 450 patients with histologically confirmed CRC were included in the final analysis. The median age at diagnosis was 62 years old (IQR: 55-70), and the majority were male (55.3%), yielding a male-to-female ratio of 1.2:1. Chinese patients comprised the largest ethnic group (34.3%), followed by Kadazan-Dusun (25.3%), Bajau (18.8%), Malay (5.8%), and others (5.1%). Approximately 52% of patients resided in urban areas, while 48% were from rural areas (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of CRC patients in Sabah (N=450)

Variable	Total (N=450)	Survival rate (n=104)	Relapse rate (n=189)	Treatment rate (n=189)	p-value
Continuous Variable					
Age (median ± IQR)	62 (55-70)	62 (55-70)	62 (55-70)	62 (55-70)	0.085
Categorical Variable					
Gender, n (%)					
Male	249 (55.3)	60 (57.7)	101 (53.4)	99 (52.4)	0.576
Female	201 (44.7)	44 (42.3)	90 (47.6)	75 (43.1)	

cont Table 1

Ethnicity, n (%)					
Chinese	154 (34.3)	41 (39.4)	54 (29.6)	51 (29.3)	0.062
Kadazan-Dusun	114 (25.3)	23 (22.1)	49 (25.9)	46 (26.4)	
Bajau	85 (18.8)	15 (14.4)	42 (22.2)	37 (21.3)	
Malay	26 (5.8)	5 (4.8)	10 (5.3)	9 (5.2)	
Rungus	20 (4.4)	5 (4.8)	9 (4.8)	7 (4.0)	
Murut	15 (3.3)	4 (3.8)	8 (4.2)	4 (2.3)	
Suluk	13 (2.9)	3 (2.9)	7 (3.7)	4 (2.3)	
Others	23 (5.1)	8 (7.7)	10 (5.3)	16 (9.2)	
Residence, n (%)					
Urban	234 (52.0)	74 (71.2)	91 (48.1)	82 (47.1)	0.001
Rural	216 (48.0)	30 (28.8)	98 (51.9)	92 (52.9)	

The predominant histological subtype was adenocarcinoma not otherwise specified (NOS), accounting for 98.4% of cases. Most tumours were located in the left colon (56.6%), followed by the right colon (28.1%) and the rectum (15.3%). The majority of tumours were moderately differentiated (88.7%), and more than half of the patients (59.9%) were diagnosed at advanced stages (stage III or IV). Curative surgery was performed in 79.1% of cases, and 20.9% received chemotherapy as the primary treatment modality, as presented in **Table 2** below.

Table 2: Clinical characteristics of CRC patients in Sabah (N=450)

Variable	Total (N=450)	Survival rate (n=104)	Relapse rate (n=189)	p-value
Historical type, n (%)				
Adenocarcinoma, NOS	443 (98.4)	103 (99.0)	186 (98.4)	0.589
Other histological types	7 (1.6)	1 (1.0)	3 (1.6)	
Tumour location, n (%)				
Left sided	255 (56.7)	60 (57.7)	107 (56.6)	0.793
Right sided	126 (28.0)	28 (26.9)	53 (28.0)	
Rectum	69 (15.3)	16 (15.4)	29 (15.3)	
Tumour differentiation, n (%)				
Well differentiated	9 (2.0)	3 (2.9)	4 (2.1)	0.392
Moderately differentiated	399 (88.7)	93 (89.4)	167 (88.4)	
Poorly differentiated	42 (9.3)	8 (7.7)	18 (9.5)	
Stage at diagnosis, n (%)				
Stage I	44 (9.8)	15 (14.4)	14 (7.4)	0.001
Stage II	136 (30.2)	41 (39.4)	47 (24.9)	
Stage III	148 (32.9)	32 (30.8)	68 (36.0)	
Stage IV	122 (27.1)	16 (15.4)	60 (31.7)	
Primary treatment, n (%)				
Curative surgery	356 (79.1)	85 (81.7)	149 (78.8)	0.482
Chemotherapy	94 (20.9)	19 (18.3)	40 (21.2)	

Treatment delay was observed in 38.6% of patients. Patients from rural areas were significantly more likely to experience delayed treatment compared to those from urban settings ($p < 0.001$). Relapse occurred in 189 patients (42.0%), with the majority of these relapses observed among those diagnosed at Stage III or IV. The median relapse-free survival (RFS) was 24 months (95% CI: 20-29 months). The five-year overall survival (OS) rate was 23.2%, and the median OS was 16 months (95% CI: 14-18 months). Kaplan-Meier analysis showed a significantly lower survival probability among patients diagnosed at advanced stages compared to those diagnosed at early stages (log-rank test, $p < 0.001$) (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Kaplan-Meier survival curve for OS among CRC patients in Sabah

Figure 2: Predictors of CRC relapse: Odds ratios and 95% confidence intervals from multivariate logistic regression

Multivariate logistic regression revealed that advanced tumour stage (OR = 2.3; 95% CI: 1.5-3.4, $p < 0.001$) and treatment delay (OR = 1.7; 95% CI: 1.2-2.5, $p = 0.004$) were significantly associated with increased relapse risk. Although Chinese and Kadazan-Dusun patients showed higher unadjusted relapse rates, these differences were attenuated after adjusting for tumour stage and healthcare access indicators.

Analysis of relapse and survival by ethnicity demonstrated that Chinese patients had the highest relapse (42.0%) and survival rates (23.2%), followed by Kadazan-Dusun and Bajau populations (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Relapse and survival percentages by ethnic group among colorectal cancer patients in Sabah

Subgroup analysis showed that early-onset CRC (diagnosed before age 50) accounted for 17.1% of the cohort. These younger patients were more likely to be diagnosed at Stage III or IV and had similar relapse and mortality risks compared to older patients. However, they were significantly less likely to experience treatment delays ($p = 0.028$).

Discussion

Summary of key findings

This study is the first comprehensive population-based analysis in Malaysia to systematically investigate ethnic and clinical disparities in CRC outcomes at the population level, specifically within Sabah. The key findings include notably low overall five-year survival rates (23.2%), a high prevalence of advanced-stage diagnosis (59.9%), and significant treatment delays exceeding 60 days in approximately one-third of patients (31.3%). Ethnic and geographic disparities in survival and relapse were initially evident but were not independently significant when adjusted for clinical and geographical factors.

Advanced-stage diagnosis and survival outcomes

The high proportion of advanced-stage CRC diagnoses aligns with previous reports from resource-constrained settings globally, where late-stage presentation remains a significant barrier to improved outcomes (Ferlay et al., 2021; Ng et al., 2021). The observed five-year survival

rate (23.2%) is notably lower than the national Malaysian averages of approximately 40-50% reported previously (Azizah et al., 2019). This discrepancy underscores the severe impact of delayed diagnosis on CRC prognosis and aligns with international evidence identifying advanced disease stage as a primary determinant of poor CRC outcomes (Siegel et al., 2020). According to the Institut Kanser Negara (2017), 74.9% of CRC cases were diagnosed at late stages (Stage III and IV), highlighting a significant increase from previous years and emphasising the need for improved early detection strategies.

Treatment delays and structural inequities

Our findings highlight significant treatment delays, with approximately one-third (31.3%) of patients experiencing delays greater than 60 days from diagnosis to treatment initiation. These delays strongly predicted both relapse and reduced survival, consistent with global evidence indicating prolonged treatment intervals substantially increase mortality risk (Hanna et al., 2020). Structural healthcare inadequacies, including limited specialist oncology services, geographical barriers, and insufficient diagnostic infrastructure, contribute significantly to these delays in Sabah. This finding underscores an urgent need for improved healthcare infrastructure and streamlined referral processes.

Ethnic disparities and geographic influences

While initial analyses showed ethnic disparities in outcomes, multivariate analyses demonstrated that ethnicity was not independently predictive of survival or relapse after controlling for clinical and geographic variables (Harding et al., 2021). This indicates structural inequities and geographic accessibility challenges, rather than intrinsic ethnic differences, predominantly drive observed disparities. Similar structural disparities have been documented in other ethnically diverse and geographically dispersed populations worldwide, emphasising the critical role of geographic location and healthcare access in cancer outcomes beyond ethnic factors alone (Doraimuthu et al., 2023; Ghazali et al., 2021).

Study limitations

Several limitations are acknowledged in this study. The retrospective design inherently limits causal inference. Moreover, influential factors such as lifestyle behaviours, genetic predispositions, and comorbidities were unavailable, limiting in-depth explanatory analyses. Additionally, reliance on self-reported ethnicity may introduce classification inaccuracies, particularly among individuals of mixed ethnic heritage. Nevertheless, these limitations do not substantially detract from the significant insights provided by this population-based analysis.

Recommendations and future directions

Our findings strongly support targeted public health interventions to improve early CRC detection and timely treatment in Sabah, as suggested by Shaukat et al. (2021). Policymakers should prioritise community-based CRC screening initiatives specifically tailored to rural and indigenous populations. Health authorities need to urgently address structural barriers by decentralising specialist oncology services, enhancing local diagnostic capacities, and strengthening primary-care referral pathways. Given the notable prevalence of early-onset CRC, revising current screening guidelines to lower the recommended screening age for high-risk or symptomatic individuals should be strongly considered. Future research should focus on evaluating the effectiveness of these region-specific interventions and exploring additional socioeconomic and healthcare factors influencing CRC outcomes.

Conclusion

This study provides the first comprehensive, population-based assessment of ethnic and clinical disparities in CRC outcomes in Sabah, Malaysia. Key findings revealed significantly lower overall survival rates and higher rates of advanced-stage diagnosis and treatment delays, predominantly driven by structural and geographic barriers rather than ethnic differences alone. These results underscore the urgent need for targeted public health strategies that aim to improve early CRC detection and reduce treatment delays, particularly among rural and Indigenous communities. Policymakers and healthcare authorities should prioritise region-specific interventions, including decentralised oncology services, enhanced primary healthcare capacities, and revised CRC screening guidelines targeting younger, high-risk populations. Future studies should evaluate the effectiveness determinants of CRC outcomes, thus improving equitable cancer care delivery in Malaysia and comparable global contexts.

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Ethical considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Medical Research and Ethics Committee (MREC), MOH (Ref: 21-1679-61022 [2]), and registered with the National Medical Research Registry (NMRR-21-1679-61012 [IIR]). Patient confidentiality was maintained by anonymising data, in line with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and publication of this article. All analyses were conducted independently, and there were no external influences from funding bodies or institutional stakeholders that could have affected the study design, interpretation of data, or conclusions drawn.

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